

RERAM

research to innovation in
resource efficiency

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Regional Research 2 Innovation Strategies and Exploitation Plan for a Resource Efficient Forest-based Sector in ENP-EaP countries

Promoting a partnership of industries, research and authorities
to foster efficient use of raw materials and a more competitive
forestry and wood manufacturing sector

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1 Objectives

This deliverable is a final WP5 activity report of the RERAM project activities to elaborate RERAM's international cooperation strategy for the integration of research actors and related future joint R&D actions in the forest-based sector and to promote increased resource efficiency, focussing on enterprises and stakeholders in the ENP-EaP countries:

- Task 5.1: Future R&D Collaboration and Pilot Projects
- Task 5.2: Synthesis of Regional Research to Innovation Strategies (R2I) and Recommendations

The task 5.1 main objective is to map the common research needs and opportunities for future collaborative R&D actions among the ENP partner countries and develop relevant new R2I actions (pilot projects).

- The proposed knowledge transfer, networking, mobility, qualification and innovation support measures shall target and involve typical SMEs in the forest-based sector and facilitate especially an easier exchange between research and business partners.
- The strategic actions propose jointly developed, complementary, interlinked cross-border activities in the form of pilot projects with a demonstrated impact on competitiveness and resource efficiency.

The task 5.2 main objective is to synthesize the project findings and conclude objectives, strategies and recommendations for R2I actors in ENP-EaP countries, aiming at enforcement of entrepreneurial power in SMEs and innovation towards resource efficiency. The concluded transfer strategies and recommendations shall put a focus to:

- A. Creation of networks and clusters as a facilitator / mediator between research and businesses, to improve the quality and practical value of scientific innovation
- B. Twinning of regional knowledge clusters in the EU and ENP countries
- C. Embedding the forest-woodworking-sector in national and international R2I initiatives
- D. Strategic innovation plans/roadmaps for sustainable development of ENP regions

CONFIDENTIALITY NOTE: This final report **D5.1** documents the state of accomplished work conducted during the period 2 between 22/04/2015 (start of WP5 at SC3 meeting) until 31/05/2016. The dissemination level of the report is RESTRICTED, because it contains confidential information of individual beneficiaries' project proposals. The report **D5.2** is a shortened PUBLIC summary version of this report.

2 Coordination of R2I strategies and pilots

WP5 was initiated during period 1 with a consortium working session during the Steering Committee Meeting SC3 in Tbilisi, Georgia, on 22/04/2015. The team worked out an initial list of follow-up strategies and proposed pilot projects, which were elaborated subsequently. RERAM beneficiaries then started to develop new cooperation related to resource efficiency of the forest-based sector with other external partners and regional stakeholders.

- A focus has been given to an early involvement of stakeholders into the strategy process. Notably the WP3 *Enterprise Checks* (see **D3.2**) and the WP4 *R2I Dialogues* (see **D4.2**) provided essential inputs for WP5: priorities and partnerships were enhanced through mutual exchange with SMEs, R2I actors and other international initiatives.
- The regional map of baselines in wood material use and the sector's R&D environment allowed for a matching of the partner regions' institutional and thematic R2I capacities. Linking different regions' proposed priorities has been used successfully to sharpen complementarities and conclude synergetic project ideas. Uncovering particular knowledge gaps and joint research opportunities triggered the development of future joint actions.
- The ENP regions' need for capacity building and promotion of specific RTI in raw materials highlights major obstacles and discrepancies in the business environment (e.g. legislation, policies, markets, education), which are addressed as 'Challenges' (see chapter 3.1). Realistic priorities and targets for the strategic actions are required.

Based on the outcomes of the WPs 2, 3 and 4, common research needs and opportunities for collaborative R&D among the ENP partner countries have been identified and strategic actions to enhance the knowledge landscape in Research 2 Innovation (R2I) of the forest-based sector have been concluded.

Required information on research and innovation programmes and funding opportunities have been collected through desktop research and partnering in R2I events. Among others, beneficiaries have attended several programmes information events, for example:

- Info day on forest-related calls under HORIZON2020, organised by the *Technology Platform of the Forest-based Sector*, held in Munich on 27 October 2015
- Info day on the *Danube Transnational Programme* of the European Territorial Cooperation (ETC), held in Budapest on 23-24 September 2015

RERAM's tangible outcomes have been assessed as to their relevance and transferability in the broader regional context of ENP countries, and beyond. The synthesis adds higher value to RERAM's outcomes: the research priorities and cooperative innovation pilots are tailor-made solutions of broader relevance for ENP-EaP countries, concluding priority objectives, recommendations and targets for R2I actors, aimed at the enforcement of the entrepreneurial power in SMEs to innovate towards resource and raw material efficiency.

3 Outlook on EU-ENP Collaboration in R2I

3.1 Challenges of the forest-based sector

The RERAM baseline study (see **D2.3**) identified the following main barriers and challenges for the forest-based sector in Eastern Europe (ENP-EaP).

1. **Undervalued raw materials:** Wood-based processing and manufacturing largely decreased, deteriorated or collapsed in most EaP countries following the end of the socialist era. Today the forest-based sector in Eastern Europe relies largely on timber raw material extraction, only basic processing and export.
2. **Undersized sector:** The forest-based sector in EaP countries is of small size compared to the national wood resource potential. The number of enterprises is small because of very difficult business conditions, unreliable availability of timber, non-effectiveness of state ownership and intransparent, complicated procedures for timber sale.
3. **Low productivity, low resource efficiency:** The production efficiency in EaP countries, e.g. in terms of output per employee, is in general much lower than in the EU. They produce fewer products in terms of turnover from 1 m³ of procured merchantable wood and from 1 m³ of overall timber stock.
4. **Lack of higher value added:** Capacities of secondary processing are not developed, which is a main barrier to promote growth in the sector. To catch up, EaP countries need considerable investments, effective hands-on support programmes to implement and upgrade new technologies, tools, equipment, market innovations and restructuring measures.
5. **Globalised markets:** EaP countries hold considerable, yet less developed forest resources with a comparatively average lower land use pressure than in Western Europe. A constantly growing demand for wood raw materials in European markets lead to higher raw material imports and growing pressure on forests that hold substantial, unexploited wood resources in neighbouring Eastern Europe. Bilateral industry initiatives, cooperative supply chains, market promotion and international knowledge transfer between ENP-EaP and EU countries are needed, to develop domestic capacities. A key challenge here is the regulatory framework that needs to be enhanced and enforced.
6. **Macroeconomic role and conscience:** The forest-based sector's share of the national GDP in EaP countries is, similar to EU countries, below 2%. A common understanding as a vital sector of the economy, which unites all subindustries, which are connected to the resource 'forest', is still inexistent in EaP countries. The main challenge is to initiate a coordinated effort of market actors and stakeholder to develop and promote adapted sustainable management regimes for the abundant resource. This is extremely important to ensure a viable balance of economic, social and environmental principles. Without such a common understanding, the forest-based sector will be unable to keep a balance between industrial growth and long-term sustainability.

3.2 Challenges of future R2I collaboration

The ENP-EaP forest-based sector's challenges, as identified and analysed in detail as part of the RERAM action, are composed of three major features:

- i) the specific topic/content of **Raw Materials & Resource Efficiency**, notably in the forest-based sector,
- ii) the claim and mission of bridging **Research to Innovation (R2I)**, and
- iii) the geographic/regional focus on the **Eastern Partnership (EaP) countries**.

The framework that allowed RERAM, a pilot action combining these three features, to be funded under the specific FP7-INCO International Cooperation programme was the dedicated call on 'Reinforcing cooperation with European Neighbourhood Policy countries on bridging the gap between research and innovation (R2I-ENP)'. This framework no longer exists in that very form.

The survey and appraisal of R2I-related programmes and funding schemes as part of the WP5 effort showed that it is difficult to identify suitable schemes that can combine these three components in one action. The new scope and direction of **HORIZON 2020**, for instance, reveals that:

- The number of **specific calls for topics related to 'forests' or 'wood'** has diminished. A few core forest research domains such as forest monitoring or wood mobilisation are still covered in specific calls, clearly aimed at the EU (and not ENP). As a result, EU-internal competition in the forest-based sector research community has increased.
- There is a **trend towards new cross-sectoral initiatives** aimed at integrating different innovative and traditional sectors or value chains, addressing the societal challenges of our increasingly interconnected world. While this makes sense as a H2020 priority, the effect is a new challenge for forest-based sector: the sector or parts of it have been redefined as a (small) part of larger cross-sectoral domains, e.g. the bioeconomy, the environment, the renewable energies, the rural development sector, to name a few. Future R2I actions require therefore not only sector internal coordination, but also coordination with external domains, which adds even more complexity to the task.
- To date, there are **no new specific ENP programme lines or calls** to be expected. The ENP-EaP partner countries Ukraine, Moldova and Georgia are full associated members of H2020, so their participation is eligible and intended. However, in this setting, R2I organisations in ENP member states have to compete on the same level as EU institutions: their R2I profile, capacity and record of excellence has to complement or at least match the required competence of an EU consortium. Practically speaking, this narrows down substantially the thematic research domains and number of potential R2I organizations as consortium members, at least in view of the forest-based sector.

In conclusion, RERAM facilitated a unique opportunity for sharing the expertise and experience in resource efficiency from EU countries with the emerging industrial sector in ENP countries. However, follow-up schemes are not evident and actions have to be well tailored to real possibilities in the international R2I domains.

4 R2I Strategies and Recommendations

4.1 Strategic goals of the ENP-EaP forest-based sector

The RERAM project successfully demonstrated that resource efficiency represents a real solution and opportunity for SMEs to improve their production and the environmental performance, while saving costs at the same time. RERAM's trainings and enterprise checks helped to generate valuable first hand information and results about tangible solutions how to best promote a sustainable development of the raw material-intensive ENP forest-based sector. The participating companies have expressed the benefit of the hands-on checks for their business, and first results of successful implementations of the saving options are already confirmed.

The project results are targeted first of all at SMEs in the forest-based sector, but also at public authorities, consultants, researchers and decision-makers in economic policy. Fostering growth and innovation of the EaP forest-based sector requires stronger communication and cooperation among all stakeholders, to stimulate a broader uptake of efficiency and cleaner production solutions in the sector, and to improve the business climate for ambitious SMEs that are well positioned to step up onto international markets. To facilitate this market uptake, the RERAM project recommends three main actions:

- First, ***joint forest-based sector initiatives*** should be formed, which can unite and join the forces of the different sub-industries and promote a better understanding and collaboration in the EaP sector. The main purpose is to assess the sector's status, barriers and potentials and develop a common vision, priorities and innovative actions. The second purpose is to raise awareness and improve the public perception of the sector's potentials for sustainable growth in the bioeconomy.
- Second, ***the principle of resource efficient use of raw materials needs to be promoted*** widely in the EaP sector. Support programs for SMES need to be set up that target the implementation of cleaner production and sustainability. The programs should aim at reduced wastes, higher recycling, less pollution and technological modernisation. The programs can include a range of methods, e.g. innovation vouchers, grants, credit schemes, enterprise checks and audits, competition and prizes, joint market promotion campaigns, and dedicated training and qualification.
- Third, the EaP sector needs a ***transformation from 'from volume to value added'***. New investments in higher level manufacturing and domestic markets need to be stimulated. Specific promotion for local wood industries is needed that support companies in the acquisition of new technology, the preparation of new investments and innovations, and facilitate the upgrade of production systems and competence.

Given the large forest resources and the considerable size of the ENP-EaP forest-based sector as a major pillar in the ENP regional economy, these actions can be expected to have decisive positive impacts on the foundation of new enterprises and the creation of higher employment in local communities.

4.2 Strategic Research Agenda of the European FTP

FTP is the European Technology Platform for the Forest-based Sector. The long-term strategy of FTP is established in its Vision 2030 to be implemented through the Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda for 2020. These documents are updated according to changing realities. InnovaWood has been intensively involved in the development of these strategic documents and in the continuous support of the strategic initiatives of FTP for the development of research and innovation activities in the European forest-based sector. Since 2005 when FTP was established, more than EUR 1 billion of public funding have been invested in cooperative research and innovation projects addressing the vision and improving the competitiveness and sustainability of the forest-based sector in Europe.

Extensive work by representatives of industry, forest owners, researchers and public bodies around Europe has gone into the establishment of the SRA. It is intended to help policymakers and funding providers at both the EU and national levels play their part in achieving the forest-based sector's vision to improve our world. Industry and researchers will find the SRA to be an important point of reference for further actions.

The European forest-based sector is affected by many of the same challenges as society: climate change, increasing competition for raw materials and the growing complexity of manufacturing processes. But challenges also provide opportunities to innovate and grow. Forest-based industries in Europe already use a natural, renewable and non-food resource in a sustainable and responsible way. By growing and evolving, this sector promises to become a key enabler of the sustainable biobased society of the future.

In this context the forest-based sector in ENP-EaP countries has real perspectives. Industries that work with solid wood are important, because they offer a tangible way to reduce CO₂ emissions that are the main cause of Climate Change, through the carbon sink effect of the forests (CO₂ absorption by trees), the carbon storage effect of wood products and the substitution of carbon-intensive materials. It is therefore paramount to address the main challenges in the forest-based sector and to elaborate concrete measures and initiatives, which can mitigate the current unsustainable practice and overexploitation.

Nineteen research and innovation areas (RIAs) have been identified by FTP as key to unlocking the potential of the European forest-based sector and ensuring its future competitiveness. The RIAs are organised under four Strategic Themes; 'The forest-based sector in a biobased society', 'Responsible management of forest resources', 'Creating industrial leadership', and 'Fulfilling consumer needs'. These RIA are described in detail in the annex to the Strategic Research and Innovation agenda 2020. Many RIA areas of the SRA are focus points for the forest-based sector in the ENP-EaP countries.

Strategic Research & Innovation Agenda 2020 - Annex Strategic Themes and Research & Innovation Areas

1. The forest-based sector in a biobased society

- 1.1 The performance of the sector in a perspective of global change
- 1.2 Citizens' perception of the sector
- 1.3 Policies and good governance

2. Responsible management of forest resources

- 2.1 Multi-purpose management of forests
- 2.2 Forest ecology and ecosystem services
- 2.3 Enhanced biomass production
- 2.4 Secured wood supply, forest operations and logistics
- 2.5 Cascade use, reuse and recycling systems

3. Creating industrial leadership

- 3.1 Resource efficiency in manufacturing
- 3.2 Renewable energy solutions
- 3.3 Sustainable water stewardship
- 3.4 Biorefinery concepts
- 3.5 New business models and service concepts

4. Fulfilling consumer needs

- 4.1 Building with wood
- 4.2 Indoor environment and functional furniture
- 4.3 New biobased products
- 4.4 Intelligent packaging solutions
- 4.5 Hygienic, diagnostic and healthcare products
- 4.6 Integration of new solutions in printed products

The entire research agenda can be consulted via this link:

<http://www.forestplatform.org/en/strategic-research-agenda/revise-sra-for-2020>

The focus on the woodworking (wood in construction and interior use) activities are of high relevance for the ENP-EaP countries. Following listed activities are prioritised for the further development of the woodworking sector in ENP-EaP countries and EU.

Interior use of wood and wooden products

- Develop technological designs for moisture controlled use of wood and wood-based products in buildings' weather barriers in different climatic conditions. Use of sensors for monitoring and control
- Clarify the role of wood and wood-based products in securing good indoor environments and contributing to perceived comfort.
- Further develop the multi-material concepts and multi-functionality for wood and woodbased products in interior fittings, furniture and everyday products.
- Develop indoor system solutions that promote flexibility regarding changes in use (ageing inhabitants, changing family structures, growing children).

- Study factors that influence people's appreciation of the aesthetics of wood, especially in interior furnishings and identify barriers preventing greater use of this sustainable and environmentally-friendly product.
- Develop environmentally-friendly multifunctional varnishes and lasuring coatings with microencapsulations (aromas, biocides, UV filter absorbents and fire retardants).
- Develop intelligent furniture surfaces (integrated sensors and electrical conductivity) and use a 'learning from nature' approach towards state-of-the-art surface qualities, durability and mechanical properties of wood-based materials.
- Develop new application systems for waterbased and powder coatings.
- Develop natural bioadhesives and other biopolymers to enhance bonding in furniture components.
- Continue to develop environmentally-friendly methods for modifying wood and improving the long-term properties of wood-polymer composites to increase their resistance to deterioration.
- Create new functional wood and composite products for home and urban furniture.
- Combine superior material properties of wood with high-level design and a segmented marketing approach.
- Develop biobased lightweight 3D furniture components.

The goal of this set of research and innovation actions is to achieve that a new generation of wood-based interior systems will be established in buildings. Wood will be successfully integrated with other materials in various types of design solutions. New wood-based materials and methods for modifying wood will be established. Wood will be considered an engineering material offering quality-proved methods to ensure durability and shape stability. Novel value-added products based on recycled wood will have entered the market. Furthermore, new generation woodbased products and biobased material systems for outdoor use with minimum maintenance requirements will be in use. Almost maintenance-free barrier systems (paints, clear varnishes, etc.) and engineering models that allow far better predictions of performance in a variety of exposure and wear situations will be developed. A new generation of intelligent furniture will adjust to the changing needs of an ageing population.

Building with wood

- Identify barriers to sustainable and environmentally-friendly construction and develop further urban building solutions.
- Harmonise building standards in Europe.
- Integrate information and production technologies in design and building information models for new generation wooden houses.
- Develop cost-effective integrated prefabricated timber building systems including hybrid and composite materials.
- Investigate human wellbeing, operational safety, structural quality and energy efficiency in wooden buildings.
- Develop design concepts taking into account changing building services during the building's lifetime.
- Improve building physics, indoor air quality and the behaviour of wooden constructions, especially in low-energy houses.

- Develop advanced non-destructive measurement systems for quality prediction and quality control in wood in construction and in wooden structures.
- Develop advanced scientifically-justified lightweight wood and fibre-based products, engineered wood products and composite materials with superior performance, low emissions, produced with novel, high quality environmentally-friendly biobased adhesives.
- Develop solutions with superior thermal and ventilation properties, positive health effects, resistance to moisture and microbial attacks in wood-based, fibre-based or ecologically-treated insulation materials and systems.
- Develop advanced wooden structure joints to improve performance and broaden the applicability of wooden structures to substitute for carbon-intensive materials.
- Improve outdoor performance of wood-based materials and develop new biobased protection treatments for wood-based products. Develop, document and offer training in methods for protecting wood through design solutions.
- Develop construction systems and biobased treatments to enhance the long-term durability of high performance wood-based products.
- Given the functional requirements imposed on the respective products, develop methods to match the lifespan of wood to that of other construction materials (holistic approach, risk of failure, lifecycle costs, lifecycle planning, strength and sustainability analysis).

The goal of this set of research and innovation actions is to achieve that Green sustainable building and green renovation practices will be fully established in Europe. That green building refers to a structure and process that is environmentally responsible and resource efficient throughout a building's lifecycle: from site selection to design, construction, operation, maintenance, renovation and demolition. Green building practice will expand and complement the classic building design concerns of economy, utility, durability and comfort. Building regulations will have functionally based requirements for product performance (fire safety, acoustics) and will not discriminate against the use of wood in multi-storey constructions. Wood-based construction methods will generally be perceived and credited as low carbon footprint constructions.

Future EU-ENP collaborations on many of these topics will receive a full support from the FTP sector. These topics of interest are still put forward by FTP towards European stakeholders and policy makers as high on the priority lists for the full development of the forest-based sector in Europe and beyond.

4.3 Thematic Priorities for EU-ENP R2I Collaboration

Based on the project findings and results, with valuable input from various regional stakeholders during the R2I Dialogues, the RERAM consortium identified the following main thematic priorities for future collaborative actions of EU and ENP-EaP R2I actors. The priorities represent topical domains for research, technological development and innovation related to RERAM's main purpose.

- **Priority 1: *Resource Efficiency, Cleaner Production and Climate Protection*** represent the core themes of the RERAM activities, aiming at an improved competitiveness and environmental performance of private companies, notably SMEs. These type of actions target technological renewal, upgrading and innovation of business models towards clean technologies and sustainable products and services, while enhancing carbon footprints and resource efficiency of raw-material intensive industries.
- **Priority 2: *Forest Research and Forest Management*** is a key domain for the forest-based sector, because it aims at safeguarding the integrity of the forest ecosystem and ensuring the long-term supply of raw wood material for the sector. R2I actions target specific barriers and challenges of this domain, but can also be integrated with wider value chain or market initiatives linked to manufacturing industries.
- **Priority 3: *Biomass, Bioenergy and Bioeconomy*** represent a top priority domain, given the importance and rapid growth of wood-based energy, biochemical and new material uses of solid biomass resources. The forest-based sector is in a unique, main contributor to renewable energies and the future bioeconomy, delivering safe, reliable sources of sustainable energy carriers and low impact materials.
- **Priority 4: *Non-wood forest products and services*** addresses as specific opportunity of the forest-based sector to develop new value added products and sources of income notably for rural communities, which represent viable alternatives to, or even beneficial synergies with traditional forestry and harvesting of raw timber (e.g. hunting, mushrooms, forest fruits, recreation, ecotourism, ecosystem services, among many others). It is of special interest to ENP countries, because of the abundant forest biodiversity and the still accessible traditional knowhow of rural populations.
- **Priority 5: *Innovation and Business Support*** is a crosscutting priority to enable business to innovate and grow in favourable conditions, having access to the right advice and tools that equip them for new and competitive markets. This is paramount for SMEs in ENP-EaP countries, and especially for the forest-based sector.
- **Priority 6: *Education, Qualification and Participation*** is another crosscutting domain, which ensures the basis of knowledge generation, knowledge transfer and innovation to the various target groups, especially young people, in the forest-based sector.
- **Priority 7: *Land Use and Regional Development*** is an important field relating to the wider role of forestry and woodworking industries as a contributor to regional or national employment and economic development.

5 Pilot project initiatives and proposals

5.1 Overview

The RERAM consortium has also developed a series of new pilot projects for national, bilateral and international funding programs, which address various aspects of the aforementioned strategies, recommendations. The consortium members have, as main applicants or in consortia of various constellations, engaging notably other regional SMEs and stakeholders, elaborated these project drafts and submitted various proposals under a wide range of national and international schemes. Some of these have even already succeeded with new granted actions. Thus several new projects have emerged and are now carried out by partnerships of different compositions. More projects are expected to come on stream in late 2016 and 2017.

Table 1 gives an overview of proposed pilot projects, which have been grouped according to the R2I priorities. Chapter 6.9 summarizes the current status of submitted project proposals and implementation of approved actions at the time of submission of this report (July 2016). For confidentiality reasons, the detailed pilot descriptions and the status report in the following are excluded from the public version of this report (D5.2).

Table 1 List of RERAM pilot project initiatives

No.	Short title	Funding scheme	Theme, keywords	Countries	Level, target group	Engaged RERAM partner(s)
Priority 1: Resource Efficiency, Cleaner Production, Climate Protection						
1	RECP Demonstration project	UNIDO	Cleaner Production, agro-food & construction sector	GE, AR	National; business, authorities	RECC
2	Resource efficiency platform	tbd	Sectorial coordination, clustering, R2I agenda, training	UA	National; research, business, authorities	UNFU, IIWH, ITD
3	Local Markets for Energy Efficiency	Ukraine State Fund for Regional Developm.	Energy cooperatives; local biomass energy	UA	Regional; Lviv Oblast Admin., Yavoriv Rayon	WPFC
4	Zero Waste Project	H2020, tbd	Efficient waste management in the forest sector	UA, GE, MD, DE, PL, BE	ENP-EaP countries; all stake-holders	UNFU, IIWH, ITD, AUG, IW
5	Resource efficiency of waste disposal sites	ZIM Germany	Environmental technologies, waste water, phytoextraction	UA, MD, DE	Bilateral; waste industry; local authorities	IIWH, WPFC, AITT

No.	Short title	Funding scheme	Theme, keywords	Countries	Level, target group	Engaged RERAM partner(s)
6	Empowering for Climate Change Adaptation	Global Green Grants	Climate Change Adaptation, environmental awareness, public campaigns	UA, SK, HU	Urban planners, architects, designers	FORZA
Priority 2: Forest Research, Forest Management						
7	Skilled foresters	Finish Fund for Local Cooperation	Capacity building; close to nature silviculture, sustainable forest management	UA, FI	Foresters, protected areas, civilians	FORZA
8	Counteracting corruption in the forest sector	International Renaissance Foundation Funds	Transparency, illegal logging, corruption, certification, corporate responsibility, public awareness	UA	Regional; Social activists, press, authorities, students	WPFC, UNFU
9	Efficiency of fast growing tree plantations	ZIM Germany	Soil enhancement, marginal lands	UA, DE	Forest authorities, agro-business, industrial parks	IIWH, WPFC
10	Sustainable Christmas tree plantations	DBU German Env. Fund	Sustainability, environmental impacts, fair trade	GE, DE, DK	Forest owners, traders, NGOs	IIWH, AUG
11	Forest genetics in Georgia	WWF	Conservation, biodiversity, genetic resources	GE	National; researchers, students	AUG
Priority 3: Biomass, Bioenergy and Bioeconomy						
12	SBC Secure Bioenergy Chains	H2020 LCE	Bioenergy market uptake, innovation vouchers, Life Cycle Assessment	South East Europe: 12 countries	SMEs in bioenergy sector; authorities	AITT, FORZA, IIWH
13	Biomass Energy	EaPTC BY-UA	bioenergy; cross border cooperation	UA, BY	Local authorities	Support by WPFC
14	Waste Efficiency in Wood Sector	EaPTC BY-UA	Biomass centres; renewable energy	UA, BY	Crossborder; Rivne Agency Reg. Dev., Brest CE	WPFC

No.	Short title	Funding scheme	Theme, keywords	Countries	Level, target group	Engaged RERAM partner(s)
15	Efficient wood energy	Int. donors	Wood fuel economics and sustainability	GE	National; various ministries	AUG
16	Bioenergy in Ukraine	Norway Ministry of Foreign Affairs	Bioenergy regional potentials; alternative energy sources	UA	Local authorities, business, citizens	WPFC
Priority 4: Non-wood forest products and services						
17	FORSOC/ Forest tourism	Norwegian Financial Mechanism	Capacity building in eco-tourism; sustainable forest management; cultural heritage	SK, UA, NO	Cross-border; Foresters, tourism agencies, students	FORZA
18	Efficient oak flavours for wine production	tbd	Wooden oak barrel alternatives	GE	Wine industry	AUG, Nanowood
Priority 5: Innovation and Business Support						
19	BUSINESS-INN-MOLDOVA	COSME (EEN)	Innovation support for resource efficiency in industry	MD	National: SMEs in all sectors	AITT
20	iCABiT	EaPTC	Innovation; cross border cooperation	MD, UA	Bilateral; innovative SMEs	AITT
21	CCI-SPACE	EaPTC MD-UA	Cultural and creative industries; cross border cooperation	UA, MD	SMEs & individuals in cultural sector	AITT
Priority 6: Education, Qualification and Participation						
22	New Competences in the wood sector	H2020, ERASMUS	Online education and qualification, modernisation of education program	UA, PL, MD, GE, ES, DE, BE	Employees in wood industries, students	UNFU, ITD, AITT, AUG, IW
23	Civil society engagement in SFM	DAAD German Academic Exc. Council	Aarhus convention, transparency, public participation	UA, DE	Bilateral; authorities, civil society, NGOs	UNFU
24	Forest sector knowledge value chain	tbd	Training centre, master course	UA, PL, AT, DE	International; SMEs, research	UNFU, IIWH, HCS, ITD

<i>No.</i>	<i>Short title</i>	<i>Funding scheme</i>	<i>Theme, keywords</i>	<i>Countries</i>	<i>Level, target group</i>	<i>Engaged RERAM partner(s)</i>
25	Regional Sustainability Managers	Europe Aid	Vocational Training, Rural development	GE, DE	Disadvantaged civil groups	RECC, IIWH
<i>Priority 7: Land Use and regional development</i>						
26	Lagodheki Pilot Initiative	Europe Aid	LEADER, Rural development, participation	GE, IE, DE	National; Local communities, farmers	RECC, IIWH
27	DETLUP	Visegrad Fund	Land Use Planning, local governance	UA, GE, MD	Bilateral; public authorities; investors	FORZA, RECC, AITT
28	SID	INTERREG Danube	Sustainable and Integrated Development	HU, CZ, SI, SE, SK, MD, UA	International ; public authorities	AITT, FORZA

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